

HOW DOES THOUGHT PENETRATE AND IMPREGNATE SPACE?

Caio César Costa Santos¹

Abstract: The philosopher Helena Roerich ([1930] 1979), once, in her work *Infinite* said stating that “thought penetrates and permeates space”. Given this previously curious statement, we decided to say a few words about this truth. The method is phenomenological. Our objective is to bring to the lay reader one of the primordial truths sometimes not known by many beings - “how it is possible for thought to penetrate the reality of space”.

Keywords: Thought. Penetrate. Impregnate. Space. Roerich.

Introduction

I begin this essay by saying that your writing, as well as what will be discussed here, has as its merit a small tribute to Mrs. Helena Roerich presented to me by Trigueirinho. According to Roerich ([1930] 1979), not just an ethereal mass of sound (like speech) *in transit* and *permeates* space, but, even before this effect, thought is its original cause. In other words, the space we know is absolutely an open field and subject to multiple conditions of existence. Space works together with time, therefore, space *suffer* the effects of the virtuality and actuality of time. In this sense, the logic of space (or its spatiality) is, in short, *transcendental*. The sense of *transcendental* does not mean exclusively that space *transcends* anything or surface, but every spatial organism *will always be open* for all types of fabrics that accommodate it. In this sense, space is, in a panpsychist sense, a “Being”; be this supernatural and transcendental. It is extremely “supernatural” because, incredible as it may seem, despite being a product and cause of Nature, space appears and happens, absolutely, without a clearly determined cause. In Nature, nothing is or can be determined because “nothing is fixed in the universe”. This, in the presence of time, appears to us to be something immediately “extraordinary”. In Creation, Time and Space are brothers of the same placenta. This means that time is shaped into space and space is shaped into time. Or, in other words, time, among infinite other things, *it drains* in the fabric of space to, above all, provoke movement in its “vacuity”.

Modern science has already witnessed and proven that empty space does not exist. Something that, since the mysticism of the primordial era highlighted in medieval times, had

¹ Phenomenological psychoanalyst. Degree in Linguistics, Philosophy and Religious Sciences. Master in Linguistic Studies.

already affirmed this. In this sense, from the 19th century onwards, the existence of a primordial substance within empty space was scientifically discovered - this substance was the “ether”. It turns out that this ether, in its nature and essence, could not “move” without the content of time. If “nothing is fixed in the universe”, then nothing is fixed because time exists. I have said this on other occasions, but, let's repeat - “it is not possible to measure, that is, to put on a scale, which importance weighs more - that of time or space”. Perhaps the Creator created both together, at the same time, at the same time. We say this because we can, as beings with divine intellect, at least perceive this inseparable union or tune. As said, not only is space half-open or an interval that opens to everything, but also time is a continuous and eternal interval. “Interval” here means “being between everything at the same time”. However, our focus here, in this essay, is to weave a few words around the following question: “how does thought penetrate and permeate space? For this, we will take as a guide the thought of Helena Roerich ([1930] 1979) in the book *Infinite*, vol. 1 and 2.

The thought in space

As an author and reader, since a certain time, I realized, in my own intimacy, that space could be a kind of “living being”. Even going against the materialist theory of knowledge of science, I still think that every thing, animate or inanimate, has life. I still believe as I described in a previous recent article², this life, distributed and permeated in everything, has as one of its primordial causes, what was scientifically discovered recently, I refer to the “ether”. In my humble opinion, science in general will still grow and be dazzled by great discoveries of new “substances” in our universe, as it was enchanted by the scientific discovery of the ether. The friendly reader might ask himself - “but why would space be a ‘living being’”? Perhaps, with a consistent and, therefore, scientific foundation, it would be difficult to at least try to conjecture some possibilities. On the other hand, what we can say here is much more in the field of mysticism than in science itself.

As we see and witness, Nature enchants not only because it exists and is before our, at first glance, physical eyes, but the known Nature has a beauty because it hides in its depths multiple and infinite mysteries. One of them is - “how does Nature manage to be in absolute connection with all things?” or another is - “where does this harmony or balance come from when sustaining all things in one eternity of time”? Thus, faced with these two fundamental questions, we would formulate another specifically - “how does the space we know manage, despite its absolute dynamics, to be ‘absolute’”? One of the characteristics of this “absolute space” (Newton) is its absolute immediacy.

² SANTOS, C. *The luminous ether*. Zenodo, 1-12, 2024.

Space is, among few things, an “absolute being” (as is time). Perhaps, as a mystery, the mind of God (or Universal Mind) being the Absolute, donated from this “the Absolute” the germ of the absoluteness of the absolute of things. Because, as illustrious painters like Michelangelo tell us or in the Christian metaphysics of Saint Thomas Aquinas, “God would be the supreme of all things”. With this meaning, we can imagine the Creator in all forms, but the one that is most acceptable and coherent, in human language, would be “the sum or set of all things”. Thus, “all things” means “all things”, those that have organic life, as well as those that are, by nature, devoid of it. It turns out that our view of space here is that “each thing exists because it has life”. In this case, space could not fail to also be a “living being”. Now, since space is a “living being” for us, what would be “alive” in itself that would enable the “penetration” of all thoughts of any being?

Before answering this question, let's now think about it. Following an Eastern tradition, transmitted to me through Alice Bailey (1927) in the book *The light of the soul* Vol, 1 and 2, (also presented by Trigueirinho), the thought would be a type of *substance*, in this case, “mental”, called in tradition - *chitta*. “Chitta” or “thought” is a type of special substance, the most abstract possible. In this sense, “thought”, human, animal or of an inorganic being, by the very creation of its nature is a “substance” like the “ether” that traverses any space, thing, surface or nature. In a very simple sense, “thought was made for thinking”. But what do you mean, “think”? What would be the act of “thinking”? In our view, “thinking” would be a dead state of thought or a “frozen thought”. From another perspective, mere “thinking” would be “a contemplative act of producing thoughts”. In one way or another, “thinking” would be the primary cause of our own thoughts. Within this, we can say - there is a supernatural and, therefore, unknown (mysterious) “force” that causes all thought to be covered by a form and, in addition, to be in connection with all things (nature or the universe). Why, how could thought being within us (perspective of materialism) penetrate the absolute of exteriority, which is space?

The philosopher Henri Bergson, despite his “vitalist” theory, perhaps did not find, in thought, “as an organ of attention to life”, its capacity to “place itself from the inside out”. Perhaps Bergson left something latent in his theory in the sense of “leaving open” the *vitality of thought*. All things in nature are not just “motor”, they are “sensorimotor”, as Bergson himself highlighted. In this sense, Bergsonian theory is also *panpsychist* because the universe (as we know it) is “motor” because it is entirely “sensory” or “sensitive” and even, from another perspective, “supersensitive”. In a very simple sense, “sensitive” means “that which feels or that which causes the awakening of the senses”. With this, we could say that here “space *feel*” or the thought *feel*? Once again, we can go back to Creation and say “God is omniscient”, which means that all things are also ‘omniscient’. “Omniscience” means “is aware or believes in the happening of all things” and, in this environment, thought would be that substance that would be “feeling everything” or even

“impregnating everything”. Here, the term “consciousness” would not fit in a more formal way because, far beyond thought, “consciousness” would become an “entity” much more superior than thought itself.

According to a linguistic tradition, thought would be an “amorphous mass” (Saussure) that, only with language (the language of man), could it manifest itself, enabling its “life” or “being-alive”. It turns out that, in psychodynamic terms, this perspective is not wrong because “thought without language is nothing and language without thought is nothing”, just like space and time, as we have seen. Every being, to acquire the status of “being”, would essentially need “language”. Thus, the so-called “language” is, like other things, also an “artifact” of the abstract, as we could speak, without fear of making mistakes, of a “language of things”; of all things, I repeat, “animate or inanimate”. We can also infer that it is a bit strange to think that a “pen” has a “mental substance” in its composition, but it is very coherent to say that “this pen has a language”. Like thought or other things, “language” is a concept that can be transparent to us or not, that is, visible or invisible, like, for example, “the language of birds”.

That said, we can first present the point of our essay - “thought, as the act of thinking a thought, *would not be possible without the existence of language*”. And, not because thought appears to us as a *acoustic image* (Saussure) in our mind (an ordered and cohesive set of lexemes), but because, above all things that are “linguistic”, language makes a “form” of thought. This is why, perhaps, in esotericism we talk about *thought-form*. Or, in other words, language, in its ontological sense, *shape* the potential fabric of thought, of all thought of any being that is, at best, “organic.” Regarding the “power of thought” (in the Spinozist sense), the “power of the mind” could, from an early age, happen without language because, beyond all theory, the “mind”, alone and by nature, is so abstract as space and time. But, what really guarantees the so-called “power of thought” is language because in addition to covering thought with “form”, it provides the soul dynamics (and why not luminous) for a given thought in space to “move”.

Therefore, “thought by itself” could never “teleport”, that is, surpass its form as an amorphous entity without the glorious presence of language. But, regarding language, its fundamental concept in relation to thought is the character of “coating”, just as a layer covers a fabric or clothing (re)clothes us. Therefore, language is the only element of nature that really covers thought (even if this thought is of an almost absolutely “abstract” nature). In this case, there is, therefore, some “force” (which we cannot identify at the moment) that performs the lining tuning that makes thought also become a “language”. As everything in the universe is “donation”, in this case, language donates its essence which is the “natural form of language”, thus and only in this way, thought leaves a constitution of “pure abstraction” and enters the “formal component of the

world”, namely, space. However, language, in itself, is not just the only element of nature that “invests” in the penetration of thought in space. We will now look at our second point – the “mind”.

According to Roerich, thought *is formed* in space as “psychic seeds”. Just as blood plasmates and/or permeates our organism, something similar happens with thought. The ability of thought to penetrate space is primarily given by the mind. It turns out that language makes thought a thought-form and, in this interval, the mind, like a sudden flash, makes thought something close to a “conscious state”. In this case, it is the mind that turns thought into “consciousness”, which means, “being aware when things happen”. It's as if it were a circuit: the language *information* the act of thinking a given thought and the mind *introjected* in this “formal particle” the status of “psychic” when the “mental form” is realized, but its content is still missing, that is, the “mental substance” or *chitta*. As every thing has its interior and exterior, in any given substance, there is, in fact, an internal and external part, each of which permeates each of its “layers”. Which means that, for example, a given internal part does not appear only as an “internal thing”, because, in a given internal part, one of its interior layers then appears, each layer of which has its external part.

Thus, in the ontological formation of thought, when it begins to permeate the matter of space, it could be said that the same thing happens. In the various and multiple layers of the internal and external parts of thought, there will be *composing* the substance of thought. In this sense, when thought was still “pure abstraction” it was far from having psychic meaning precisely because thought itself would necessarily be an “amorphous mass”. So, with language (embodiment) and the mind (representation), it is as if thought really became what we know as a “psychic mass” or “psychic content”. Thus and only thus can we speak of a “mental substance”. On the other hand, the mind “sensorizes” thought in the sense that thought, only through the mind, acquires a sense or a content of sensitivity. Therefore, all thought is only sensitive or only feels because the mind makes it a type of “sensory” organism, since the mind as we know it is the “primary organ of sensitivity” because, only from there, one could speak of a “perception” or the “formation of any perceptual act (real or imagined)”.

It turns out that now we can go to the third point which would be – “time”. With thought taken on the characteristic of “form” and this “form” filled with “content” donated by the mind, there still remains that which will propel the movement or dynamics in the fabric of space. As time is, at all points, there is, in some way, a “pulsating temporal life”. A curious note: “and it is incredible once again to realize that ‘nothing is really fixed in the universe’”. You wear, dear reader, like time or its temporality, it really is a “transcendental” thing and also a Reality that, perhaps, it will never be possible to decipher its entire masterful composition. If we are to talk about space, there is a dynamic in it originating from time that gives its temporality a germ of self-moving temporal life, having an even greater and absolute impact on the dynamics of atoms in all types of

matter. As stated in the introduction to this essay, there is an “empty space”, which is why space alone would not be absolutely capable of moving all things, whether material or not. He would then need the temporal organism.

Thus, time can only spread in the tissue of some organism (organic or not) through at least one *shape*. This form could then be given the meaning of the language of things. Time, despite also being a “pure abstraction”, cannot make things “temporal”, that is, “subject to the current of life”, without this given “substance” having, at its limit, a given *shape*, such “form” being - “abstract” or “concrete”. Having a “form”, it would also have a “surface” and that is where the space enters not as a “form” either, but as a “covering”. Therefore, thought now being a *thought-form* “electrified”, that is, constituting within and within oneself the vitality of magnetism and electricity (esoteric sense) as the mind moves from the state of the dead form to the “dynamic” one, composing the thought of the “vitality of a life psychic” and, here at this point, time will make this “dynamic” “even more vivid and colorful”, then it will make it possible for thought, in the form of a language and in the form of a true mental substance, to emerge from its latent state and solitary (within the organism) for the *outside* of its own existence, namely, space.

Finally, the fourth and final point would be - the “ether” or “ethereal energy”. It turns out that the entire process that we formulated here, which goes from “formalizing” thought through language to the introjection of a “psychoactivity” into it and the donation of a corpuscle of temporality to thought, we reach the point that is, firstly, beyond primordial here. Perhaps this was the formation of thought into a “form”. It would be “ethereal energy”. And more specifically, in its “luminous” form, that is, the “luminous ether”. We take, then, the luminous ether not in its “formal” or “material” form (ethereal substance), but in its “immaterial” and/or “transcendental” form (in the form of purely an “energy”). The ether, par excellence, still being a mystery to modern humanity, makes it difficult for us to convey what happens, in a complete or absolute way, when, for example, “a given thought begins to take a form” or even “when the thought becomes something about the psyche.” Only, in the glimpse of our imagination, without affirming anything, can we, in the dark, with the help of the luminosity of the intellect, weave a few words about.

The ether in/from space. At the moment when a certain living being (man) *thinks*, he *transmits*, of the frequency energy of your “mind”, luminous (electromagnetic) rays that are, at the same time as they appear, filled with spatial ether (or “space ether”). Therefore, we say, in another place, that the ether would also be a type of “living being”. Because, otherwise, if there is no “life” in the ether, how could it permeate space, or rather, how could it have a “certain type of ‘activity’” (still unknown to us) of having the capacity, intrinsic to it, of *penetrate* the whole body, abstract or not? We can say that it would be the ether, in its luminous (electromagnetic) form, that would come into contact with the entire thought-form; from its formation process as a “psychic material thing”.

By this, we mean that thought, by itself, in its “dead” phase, was already, even so, composed of “ethereal matter” simply because thought as itself could only be a “thought-being” with the existence of that most primary substance of all, especially with regard to its characteristic of “covering all things with energy”.

So, when thought begins to “possess” a “form” (even though it is still “abstract”), the means or form in which the ether now begins to “impregnate” it is different simply because thought has become simply a “form” through language. In this sense, we can say that the “being” of the “ether” is other, it would be “another thing”. Or rather, the type of energy when thought penetrates and permeates space is different. Why, let us repeat, “how does thought itself penetrate and permeate space”? Roerich himself uses a beautiful metaphor - “the psychic seeds”. Therefore, for her, thought, when it is in full activity, disseminates “psychic seeds” in space (apparently “empty”, but full of unknown “beings” and/or “organisms”). This is a reality and we can clearly perceive the effect of this without much difficulty or effort as when *we think* (or the worst *we pronounce* “inadequate” or even “negative” words), in this way, we immediately perceive a feeling that something somewhat dark (and/or dark) is present. *happening*. According to Roerich, and we faithfully agree, space (as a “living being” that it is) absorbs everything, absolutely everything, that is, everything that is composed, just like it, as a “form”). Thus, if according to mystics, thought is a *thought-form*, then, it is clear that it really as “form” that it is, *penetrates* the space. And, even more ascendantly, *permeates everything*. Therefore, by permeating everything, it leaves, in the very fabric of the space, the record or archive of that “psychic act”. This is why thought, even as a seed, creates, in the “earth of space”, its consequent “germination”.

Given this, we could take advantage of this thought and ask ourselves - “what would really be the cause of the tragedy of this surface world”? And then we would respond categorically, that is, without fear of making mistakes - the cause of the situation, if possible human, of this era, is thought. Therefore, we can really think about how many thoughts humanity, that is, the “collective consciousness”, has introduced into this terrestrial space that has not, consequently, mired the world in a hole full of mud. From this, we can understand one thing - “does the individual, at this time, think more positively or negatively”? For example, in a war context, is all thought “beneficial” or “harmful”? We wouldn't need to respond, would we? Furthermore, the tune of thought with the space around us is as clear as the tune of a hummingbird with its flower. In this regard, it turns out that if only animals (or the animal kingdom) were the only inhabitants of this Earth, it is very clear to see that the world would not become the chaos and/or abyss that it is today. So, in this sense, let's think: “how much do we think this space, in this case on Earth, is contaminated”? Thus, the catastrophic reality of this environment in which we live and share experiences is really the result of

a series of evil actions or acts or... even before this there would be the previous form of the sound act (the word), which would be “thinking”, the “ think a thought” or, at best, the “thought” itself?

In this essay, the question could go on for a very, very long time, because the problem of thought penetrating or permeating space is a problem of ages that there is, in the entire terrestrial environment, not even a hint of its appearance. But, what remains? There is clearly a remnant of the thought that was and is now (law of time). Therefore, dear reader, as Roerich himself stated, “are we or are we not responsible for our thoughts”? A given thought can make us an angel or, on the contrary, a devil. So, if you follow the Law of Life....

Conclusion

As a way of concluding this short essay, we could ask ourselves: “what would be the reality of life, in this case, “psychic”? What is, in fact, behind our thinking? Speech has power and thought, doesn't it? What would be the limit of “thinking”? Or, frankly, what would “thinking” really be? Was Universal Thought the creation of all things? Well, we can still ask hundreds of these questions, but can't we, even in today's time, discover the following - “what our ancestors really thought”? Not knowing from what is written, but from what is thought, what was behind every thought of each individual in the previous era? However, we know, or rather, we perceive something very real - “the illness or, worse, the putrefaction of the flesh of the world and why not also of ourselves. And, thinking about it, this as an original cause, couldn't it be precisely “thought”? We will leave the question open.

REFERENCES

BAILEY, A. *A luz da alma*. vol. 1 e 2, Agni Yoga Society, 1927.

ROERICH, H. *Infinito*. vol, 1 e 2, Agni Yoga Society, 1930.